

COMPOSITES FOR THERMAL MANAGEMENT
IN U.S. NAVY'S ELECTRONIC PACKAGING

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ABSTRACT

The need for more efficient electronic packaging has required the U.S. Navy to investigate improved methods of thermal management. This may be accomplished by increased volume efficiency and improved thermal performance of electronic components that make up an electronic system. One of these components is the Standard Electronic Module (SEM). The structural component of these modules is the module frame, which also is the thermal conduction path for passive cooling of the SEM. Composites including aluminum/graphite, copper/graphite, and epoxy/graphite are the primary focus of this investigation. Properties that make these materials attractive for this application are high thermal conductivity of the graphite fibers and the tailorable Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) of the composite material. Weight savings is also a significant feature of these materials for avionics applications. The composite module frame was designed to meet the mechanical, environmental, and thermal performance requirements of the SEM Format E and evaluated in accordance with those requirements. Composite architecture issues for these module frames were also investigated. Other items being considered for composite materials include CTE controlled printed wiring boards and heat spreaders in electronic component packages. Discussion will address the continuing and future work in this area, which includes optimizing the composite architecture of the module frame and future applications of composites for thermal management in electronic packaging.

KEYWORDS: Composites, Graphite, Standard Electronic Module(SEM), Thermal Conductivity, Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

1. INTRODUCTION

Electronic components are becoming more complex and at the same time becoming more densely packaged and decreasing in size. The need for a more efficient method of dissipating the heat generated by these components exists. It is known that as temperature of the integrated circuit(IC) decreases the reliability of the IC and in turn of entire systems will increase. Figure 1 is representative of MIL-HDBK-217E, Reliability Prediction of Electronic Equipment. Weight and volume limitations for systems used in avionics and shipboard electronics requires more volume efficient packaging of these components. In addition to increased volume efficiency, thermal management of these electronics must be enhanced. This may include active and passive methods of dissipating the generated heat. Passive methods include physical configuration and/or materials. A component of these electronic systems is the Standard Electronic Module(SEM). Electronic components make up these SEMs along with connecting and structural components, that have been made standard so that the modules are easily replaced if required. The structural component in these SEMs is the module frame. See Figure 2 for a diagram of the components that make up a SEM. As can be seen in this figure the module frame is a major component and influences component temperature for guide rib conduction cooling. Guide rib conduction cooling is a method of dissipating the heat out of SEMs by using the various components as thermal paths to the cardrail, which has either water or air traveling through the cooling ducts and out of an enclosure. The objective of this work was to use new materials and techniques to improve the thermal performance of electronic systems. The composite work focused on corrosion protection of aluminum/graphite heatsinks and development of techniques to adequately machine continuous fiber composite material. Development of metal and polymer matrix composites will be the desired result for SEM heatsinks. Using the fact that composite materials can be CTE controlled, these materials can also be used to constrain epoxy PWBs.

JUNCT. TEMP. VS. FAILURES / 1000000 HRS

FOR HIGH FREQ. SI-MOS DEVICES

Figure 1

Figure 2

COMPONENTS FOR GUIDE RIB CONDUCTION COOLING

2. REQUIREMENTS

Standard Electronic Modules must meet the mechanical and environmental requirements of MIL-STD-1389, MIL-M-28787, and MIL-C-28754. The use of composite materials require that additional requirements be specified. This is necessary due to the fact that material properties of the composite may be tailored in any of three directions(X,Y, and Z). That is, properties such as thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion may be specified in accordance with specific application requirements. However, some tradeoffs in these directional properties may be necessary to obtain the optimum configuration. Density of the composite material may also be tailored if it is required for a specific application.

3. ACCOMPLISHMENTS AND COMMENTS

Development of a Module Thermal Analysis Computer Program and a Component Thermal Analysis Computer Program that can be used on an IBM pc or compatible was performed. The Module Thermal Analysis Program is used to predict temperatures at the circuit board surface given certain power load and guide rib temperatures. The Component Thermal Analysis Program is used to predict component junction temperatures given power load and the temperature of the base of the package. Both programs have the capability of varying the materials used in the package, circuit board, and heatsink. These programs will be used to determine potential benefits from the use of advance materials, such as Aluminum Nitride(AlN) substrates for circuit boards, diamond films, and composite heatsinks. Modeling of the composite heatsink has included varying the quantity and direction of fibers closest to the surface of the heatsink. It was concluded, as one might expect, that the outermost layer of fibers should be in the X-direction. X-direction is, in this application, the direction in which thermal conductivity should be maximized. The results did vary depending on the distribution of the heat load. Two cases was run. Those being a lumped(less uniformly distributed) and an almost entirely uniformly distributed heat load. In all cases thermal performance was improved by having the X-direction fibers in the outermost layer. However, in a lumped distribution the Y-direction fibers assist in spreading the heat load.

Much of the work on graphite/aluminum composites has focused on the prevention of corrosion between the graphite and the aluminum. The key to this prevention seems to be to isolate the graphite/aluminum interface from the environment. One such method that has obtained good results has been to Ion Vapor Deposition (IVD) additional aluminum on the graphite/aluminum composite. This IVD process isolates the interface from the environment with a layer of aluminum. The composite that has been subjected to the IVD process can then be treated to protect the aluminum base material from the environment. Such treatments that have proved successful are anodizing, chromate coating, a ceramic coating, and a teflon coating. The effectiveness of these finishes can be evaluated by subjecting samples to the MIL-STD-810 48-hour salt fog test. Work at the Naval Postgraduate School investigated corrosion characteristics of graphite/aluminum composite. The composite was found to be susceptible to several different forms of corrosion attack in 3.5% NaCl aqueous solution. The most vigorous attack occurred at exposed graphite/aluminum interfaces. The pH factor of the solution was varied from 4 to 8. The composite was more susceptible to corrosion when immersed in a solution of pH 4 than in pH 8. This work confirms other data that indicated if the edges of the composite are protected from the environment accelerated corrosion will not occur until localized corrosion perforates the composite's surface foil.

Composite material that NWS Crane has received has undergone some evaluation in accordance with SEM heatsink requirements. Metal matrix composite material with various protective finishes have been subjected to salt fog tests and thermal conductivity measurements. All material that has been IVD aluminum has gone through the salt fog test without base material corrosion. Metal matrix composites have also been measured for flatness and surface roughness. Some material remains unsatisfactory with respect to flatness and surface roughness. In addition, some machinability evaluation has been done using conventional tooling. Some material appears to be more susceptible to delamination when machined depending on the process used to manufacture. Thermal conductivity measurements have also been made on the organic matrix composite material and the value was 405 W/m K in the X-direction, but coefficient

of thermal expansion of this material was negative.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The development of composite heatsinks will continue. Work should focus on reproducibility of composite heatsinks in a manufacturing mode. If a major system or program found it necessary to incorporate composite heatsinks because of weight limitations or required thermal performance this reproducibility may be possible.

5. BIOGRAPHY

Currently employed at the Naval Weapons Support Center, Crane, Indiana. Employed there since 1981. Has been in the Packaging Design Branch at Crane since 1986 specializing in U.S. Navy electronic hardware development. Graduated from Purdue University in 1981 with a Bachelor Degree in Aeronautics and Astronautics Engineering. Currently pursuing a Masters of Mechanical Engineering from Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology.

